

THE TEACHER'S ROLE IN TEACHING CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS

Turdiyeva Rakhima Kurbanovna

Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7808827>

Abstract. *This article discusses the pedagogical creativity of the teacher, the ability of the creative potential, its importance, the ways of its development, the components and criteria that develop creativity.*

Keywords: *pedagogical creativity, creator, creative potential, activity, development, intellect, initiative, approach, pedagogical problem, component, criterion, activity.*

Introduction. Today, it is important to provide students with modern education, to teach them to think creatively, critically, logically, and to develop the competencies of being able to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in life. This requires intellectual knowledge, high ability, creative potential and pedagogical skill from teachers. Because with the passage of time, the environment, conditions, situation and people change. In particular, the interests and needs of students will change. Also, the rapid development of science and technology, information technologies and many achievements in this field, innovations in the educational system, put high demands on the qualification level of pedagogues. Based on these requirements, teachers are required to have a deep understanding of specialized subjects, to be able to understand news in a timely manner, to keep up with the times, to be able to organize lessons using the latest advances in science and technology, and to work tirelessly on their own. is enough.

Another of the modern demands placed on the teacher is to teach students creativity, creativity, independent, critical, logical thinking. Before forming such skills in young people, the teacher needs to have a little creative ability, to be aware of the news, and to work on himself perfectly.

Literature review:

In order to understand the essence of the process of developing the creative potential of teachers, it is necessary to understand the concept of "Creativity". According to the American psychologist P. Torrens, "creativity is a problem or putting forward scientific hypotheses; hypothesis testing and modification; identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results; it expresses sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem" [3, p. 86]. According to English scientist Ken Robinson, "creativity is a set of original ideas with their own value" [6, 74 p.].

American psychologist Gardner explains this concept in his research as follows: "creativity is a practical action performed by a person, which should reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value" [7, 110 b.] According to the results of the analysis, Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" creator) means the creative ability that describes a person's readiness to develop new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. represents A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent. Creativity is a factor of self-development of a person, the basis of personal vitality, multifaceted knowledge possessed by a person, but also in the pursuit of new

ideas and in the process of reforming and changing established stereotypes in the process of creating new things, in the process of solving unexpected life problems. and is manifested in making unusual decisions.

Discussion and results

The creative qualities of a teacher depend on their personal abilities, knowledge and accumulated personal experience. Also, a pedagogue with creative qualities takes an expressive approach to the teaching process, is active in promoting advanced ideas that encourage students to think, pays attention to familiarization with best practices and new educational methodical literature.

The study of creativity is mainly carried out in two directions:

Direction 1. Issues related to creativity and intelligence and creativity

learns to define educational processes related to

Direction 2. The personality and its psychological uniqueness are the basis of creativity is classified by the fact that it is an aspect, emphasizing the person and his motivational lines

Pedagogical creativity (creativity) is the ability of a pedagogue to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as to positively solve existing pedagogical problems, in contrast to traditional pedagogical thinking.

"Pedagogical creativity" must be able to guarantee the following two conditions:

1) attracting the attention of students who have low mastery of academic subjects and consider them boring to study the basics of science by teachers;

2) to create an opportunity for teachers to use them effectively in the classroom by recommending strategies and tools that serve to stimulate students' creative thinking and creative activity results.

The development of the teacher's creativity is of great importance, and it is considered the result of creative activity. This quality represents the teacher's ability and readiness to express himself. On the basis of creative potential, the personal abilities, natural and social strength of each specialist are manifested as a whole. Creative potential is closely related to creativity focused on the cognitive process. The teacher's creativity, in contrast to traditional thinking, is manifested in:

- speed and flexibility of thinking;
- ability to create new ideas;
- not to think in one way;
- originality;
- initiative;
- Tolerating uncertainty;
- to be intelligent

In order for teachers to have the potential for creativity, it is necessary to pay attention to the following in their professional activities:

- creative approach to professional activity;
- show activity in creating new ideas;
- independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences;
- sharing ideas with colleagues about pedagogical achievements

A creative teacher is required to achieve creativity, to continue the creative work that has begun, to overcome difficulties in cognitive activities, to plan and sequence mental actions, to search for ways and methods to achieve the goal. Also, a person has sthenic feelings (a sense of

joy from cognitive and creative activity, readiness to overcome difficulties in the process of inventions, pride in achieving a cognitive or creative goal, enjoyment of the opportunity to invent something, optimistic activity at the beginning of creative work, waiting for its positive result, calmness in case of failures, etc.) is also formed. It is desirable for a teacher to find and develop such psychological processes.

Self-development and self-expression of each teacher is directly related to his creativity. Usually, the ability of pedagogues to be creative means to try to solve pedagogical problems, to approach classes in a different way, to make students interested in classes, to increase their creativity by giving unusual tasks, to carry out scientific research works or scientific projects, and to engage in mutual creative cooperation. provided by their achievements. His creative ability is formed over a certain period of time through consistent study and work on himself, and it gradually improves and develops. It is necessary to pay special attention to creating problematic situations, solving problematic issues, analyzing them, as well as creating creative products in the educational process. While solving problematic issues and situations, the pedagogue's creative approach to finding a solution to the problem helps him develop emotional and volitional qualities. By putting problematic issues in front of him, the pedagogue confronts the evidence that contradicts his existing knowledge and life experiences. As a result, he feels the need to work on himself, study independently.

The process of developing creativity in teachers includes the following structural components (see Figure 1).

A teacher with creative potential can demonstrate the following skills:

- being able to determine the nature and importance of the task to be performed;
- to be able to analyze the issue;
- making a plan to solve the problem;
- effective methods for problem solving (analysis, synthesis,

- application of induction, deduction, comparison, etc.;
- to be able to choose the methods of solving the problem;
- justifying and rechecking the correctness of the decision;
- conducting a small research (research) in solving the problem;
- condition of solving the problem, progress of the process and solution of the problem
- Formalizing the evidence for summarizing the results

It is important to assess the teacher's level of creativity, and it is determined by the following criteria: (Figure 2):

Conclusion and practical suggestions

Analyzes show that in order to have high indicators of teacher creativity, the following should be followed:

- Constantly developing his knowledge;
- Constantly improving his pedagogical experiences.
- Know the latest innovations in the field and use them
- be able to use it appropriately and effectively in their work
- Being creative.
- Knowing the age, individual and psychological characteristics of children and the teacher should act accordingly.
- Having innovative features.
- Improving the working conditions of the teacher

It is necessary to regularly enrich the teacher's creative activity with innovative innovations. Also, a creative pedagogue should pay attention to the following during the educational process:

1. Establish a friendly relationship with students.
2. Creating a positive environment in education.
3. Breaking stereotypes.
4. Make students more active.
5. Divide into groups.
6. Encouraging success in students
7. Avoid uniformity
8. Connecting information with real life.
9. Using different approaches in the lesson

In short, pedagogical activity is a process of constant creativity, which requires the teacher to develop creativity, self-development, keep up with the times, be able to think freely, and teach students to think creatively and freely. It is required to organize education taking into account the individual capabilities of students, to apply the most effective methods of assimilation to the educational process. It also supports and guides students' thoughts, encourages interesting ideas, analyzes unsuccessful attempts, encourages students to realize defeats and victories.

REFERENCES

1. Drapeau Patty. Sparking student creativity (practical ways to promote innovative thinking and problem solving). - Alexandria - Virginia, USA: ASCD, 2014.
2. Faizullayeva N. Pedagogical knowledge - professional teacher theoretical basis of skill //Continuous education j. - T.: 2006. No. 6. - p. 102
3. Basics of creative pedagogy. Tashkent. 2016
4. Creative pedagogue. Handbook. Tashkent. 2022. @krepeduz.